

Fair Allocation of Indivisible Goods: Experimental Analysis

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Abstract

Even though the fair allocation of indivisible goods is a highly active theory field, practical applications remain scarce. Hence, we provide implementations of algorithms used for computing fair allocations, alongside a thorough investigation into fairness metrics such as envy-freeness and price of fairness, as well as efficiency metrics as runtime. The aim is to obtain an in-depth understanding of the practical performance of these algorithms. The experiments indeed revealed the superior performance of simple algorithms when compared to more complex ones designed to achieve optimal results in worst-case scenarios.

Research Ethics Approval

This project obtained approval from the Informatics Research Ethics committee.

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Declaration

I declare that this thesis was composed by myself, that the work contained herein is my own except where explicitly stated otherwise in the text, and that this work has not been submitted for any other degree or professional qualification except as specified.

A handwritten signature in black ink, consisting of stylized initials and a long horizontal stroke extending to the right.

(Aloia Iglesias Roman)

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivations

In a world with scarce and limited resources, the fair distribution of goods becomes a critical issue. The allocation of indivisible goods, which are items that cannot be divided without losing their functionality or value, represents a significant challenge with ethical and social implications. Consequently, this dissertation is focused on the exploration and further study of this subject.

The allocation of indivisible goods is an interdisciplinary issue that intersects with economics, politics, ethics, and computer science. Beyond its academic relevance, the principles of this topic are used in multiple scenarios, from daily activities to governance. The extent of the algorithms discussed in this dissertation ranges from tasks as ordinary as the distribution of household chores to the allocation of public services in a country. These algorithms play an essential role in the optimization of resource allocation, making them a primary focus of this dissertation. The study and analysis of their behaviour across various scenarios will show their effectiveness and applicability in different contexts.

In particular, the concept of the allocation of goods is tightly bound to ethics, given that one of its core principles is the sense of justice and fairness when distributing the goods. Determining what qualifies as a 'fair' allocation is not a trivial task in itself. Fairness can be determined by various notions such as envy-freeness (George and Marvin, 1958) (Varian, 1973) or proportionality (Steinhaus, 1949). Considering that access to resources often determines the opportunities available to individuals, this matter also has significant social implications. Hence, understanding the basis of a fair distribution becomes a priority.

Given all the contexts in which fair allocation can have a significant impact, this dissertation aims to explore the existing methodologies and conduct a detailed analysis of their performances. Its objective is to contribute to the ongoing research regarding fairness and the distribution of resources.

1.2 Project aims

In-depth investigation into the fair allocation field started with Steinhaus (1949), who officially formalised the problem. Since then, numerous achievements and discoveries have emerged; however, most of these work has been focused on the theoretical side. Recently, one of the main lines of work has been the fair allocation of indivisible goods, leading to the development of notions such as envy-freeness up to one good or envy-freeness up to any good. Nevertheless, there is scarce work concerning the empirical side of the field.

The primary objective of this dissertation is the thorough examination of the existing methodologies designed to address this distribution challenge. Specifically, our focus lies on evaluating the Round-Robin, the Envy-cycle Elimination and the Minimum Price of Fairness algorithms for both two and n-arbitrary agents. We aim to assess whether a theory that does not follow a criterion for the worst-case scenario, could do so in practice.

We study the performance of the aforementioned algorithms through the execution of multiple experiments across various scenarios. These experiments utilize both real data provided by users and generated data, which allows us to have greater control over the experimental configuration and conduct more targeted tests. The experiments focus on the examination of three notions related to fair allocation: fairness metrics, runtime evaluation and price of fairness. The ultimate goal is to compare the algorithms to draw significant conclusions about their efficiency, simplicity and scalability. We aim to find any trade-offs between these attributes.

Focusing on the empirical aspects allows us to provide meaningful insights into practical applications. Consequently, although our results may not lead to absolute conclusions, they manage to show the algorithms' behaviour. Given the relevance of the fair allocation of indivisible goods, it is essential for us to emphasize this empirical side.

1.3 Contributions

The principal contributions of this dissertation are the following:

- Acquiring a deep understanding of the fundamental problem of allocating indivisible goods, along with a study of the related mathematical concepts and notions.
- Implementing the Round-Robin and Envy-cycle elimination algorithms that were previously implemented in other papers (Amanatidis et al., 2022). Additionally, we managed to implement the Minimum Price of Fairness for two and n-arbitrary agents algorithms for the first time. This represents a novel achievement in the field. The code implementation is available in this GitHub repository ¹ so that these algorithms can be used in future experiments.
- Comprehensive set of experiments to analyse the fairness metrics (envy-freeness,

¹<https://github.com/Aloia2002/MInf-part1-.git>

envy-freeness up to one good, and envy-freeness up to any good), runtime and price of fairness associated with the four analysed algorithms.

- Drawing relevant conclusions about the behaviour and performance of the algorithms, which can be proved useful for future practical applications in this domain.

1.4 Dissertation structure

The dissertation is divided into four principal chapters.

Chapter 2. Background: It serves as a fundamental groundwork. It focuses on providing the mathematical knowledge and conceptual framework essential to understanding the intricacies of the project.

Chapter 3. Implementation: It offers a detailed description of the code. Here, we provide a thorough analysis of each class, emphasizing the use of specific data structures, as well as, addressing the challenges encountered along the way.

Chapter 4. Experiment: It becomes the central point for empirical investigation, including a diverse range of performed experiments and the resulting findings. The first subsection focuses on the data used for the experiments, exploring the various sources from which it was obtained. Following this, the chapter is further divided into three essential subsections, categorizing experiments based on their focus on fairness analysis, runtime evaluation or exploration of price of fairness.

Chapter 5. Conclusions: It finalizes the dissertation by summarizing the key takeaways obtained during the project. We also include here a synthesis of the results obtained in the previous chapter, concluding with a reflection on this dissertation's achievements. As this constitutes the first phase of our MInf work, we elaborate on next year's topic and how it relates to the current one.

Chapter 2

Background

Fair allocation is a field not only related to computer science but to politics, economics, philosophy and mathematics. Its applicability ranges from everyday problems, such as sharing rent among flatmates or task distribution in a group project, to more significant endeavours like allocating goods between a set of individuals, being this the focus of the project.

The fair allocation of goods was officially formalised by Steinhaus (1949), who introduced the ‘cake cutting’ problem. However, this has been a recurring issue since Ancient Greece when Aristoteles (1887) already considered the allocation of scarce resources a moral issue. It was not until the past few decades that significant progress has been made in this matter. Nonetheless, the main focus of the research was related to the fair allocation of infinitely divisible goods. Aziz and Mackenzie (2016) recently proved that it is possible to do an envy-free and proportional allocation of these divisible goods in a finite number of steps.

But there is another possibility: what if the goods are indivisible? This presents a more intricate and challenging question. Exploring whether it is always feasible to achieve a fair allocation with indivisible goods and the analysis of allocation algorithms is the focal topic of this dissertation.

2.1 Fair allocations

First and foremost, it is essential to know when an allocation is considered to be fair. This allocation is held in a context in which there is a set of agents N and a set of goods M to distribute, with $n = |N|$ number of agents and $m = |M|$ number of goods. Each agent assigns a value to each of the goods with a valuation function v . Taking this into consideration, there are three notions related to fairness: envy-freeness (EF), proportionality (Prop) and equitability.

An allocation is considered envy-free if no agent wants to change their apportionment with another agent. In the same way, for an allocation to be proportional, each agent has to receive their ‘fair share’ in terms of the total value of the goods. Lastly, equitability

refers to the fact that all agents should have the same value for their allocations. Our main focus is on the notion of envy-freeness.

2.2 Envy-freeness

The problem of analysing whether an instance admits envy-freeness alone is NP-complete and in most of the cases, it is not possible to find this type of allocation. The trivial and simplest case is the situation of having two agents but just one good; no matter the allocation, there will always be an agent who is envious of the other. For this reason, certain relaxations of this notion exist.

2.2.1 Envy-freeness up to one good (EF1)

The first relaxation is envy-freeness up to one good (EF1), formally defined by Budish (2011). An allocation is considered to be EF1 if for every pair of agents $(i, j) \in N$:

$$v_i(A_i) \geq v_i(A_j \setminus \{g\}) \text{ for some } g \in A_j$$

This approach states that it is acceptable if an agent i envies the bundle assigned to another agent j as long as by removing one object from agent j 's bundle, the envy also disappears. There are three well-known algorithms with which we can achieve this property: Round-Robin, Envy-cycle Elimination and Maximum Nash Welfare.

Definition 2.2.1 (Round-Robin). The Round-Robin algorithm achieves to assign the goods to the agents in multiple rounds in polynomial time. In each iteration, following an arbitrary order, the agents choose their most valued good from the ones that have yet not been assigned to anyone else. It is not difficult to prove that this algorithm always leads to an EF1 allocation.

Algorithm 1: Round-Robin (RR)

Input: A fair allocation instance $I = (N, M, v)$ with n agents and m goods.

Output: Allocation $A = (A_1, \dots, A_n)$.

for each agent $i \in N$ **do**

 | $A_i \leftarrow \emptyset$

end

for $\ell = 1$ **to** m **do**

 | Let $i \leftarrow \ell \bmod n$

 | Let $g^* \in \arg \max_{g \in M} v_i(g)$

 | $A_i \leftarrow A_i \cup \{g^*\}$

 | $M \leftarrow M \setminus \{g^*\}$

end

We have just mentioned that Round-Robin is a polynomial time algorithm, but what exactly does this mean? An algorithm A is considered to have polynomial runtime if the number of steps required to complete such algorithm for a given input is at worst $O(n^k)$, where k is a non-negative integer and n represents the complexity of the input. Any

other algorithms that cannot be resolved in $O(n^k)$, exhibit ‘superpolynomial’ running time, which often, in practice, is in fact exponential, i.e., $O(2^n)$.

Definition 2.2.2 (Envy-cycle elimination). Moving on now to the second algorithm, the Envy-cycle Elimination, which was introduced by Lipton et al. (2004). This algorithm maintains an envy-graph, where the nodes represent the agents and the edges represent the envy among those agents. In this algorithm, each good at a time is assigned to a source - an agent that is not envied by anyone else. If there are no sources, this implies the existence of a direct cycle which can be solved by rearranging the assigned bundles. We repeat this step until we can find a source to whom the next available good can be assigned. It is implicitly proved by Lipton et al. (2004) that this algorithm can achieve an EF1 allocation in polynomial time.

Algorithm 2: Envy-Cycle Elimination (ECE)

Input: A fair allocation instance $I = (N, M, v)$ with n agents and m goods.

Output: Allocation $A = (A_1, \dots, A_n)$.

for each agent $i \in N$ **do**

$A_i \leftarrow \emptyset$;

end

for $\ell = 1$ **to** m **do**

while there does not exist an unenvied agent **do**

 Find an envy-cycle $C = (i_1, \dots, i_d)$ and resolve the cycle as follows:

$$A_{i_j}^C = \begin{cases} A_{i_{j+1}} & \text{for all } 1 \leq j \leq d-1 \\ A_{i_1} & \text{for } j = d \end{cases}$$

$A_i \leftarrow A_i^C$ for all $i \in C$;

end

 Let i be an unenvied agent;

 Let $g^* \in \arg \max_{g \in M} \{v_i(g)\}$;

$A_i \leftarrow A_i \cup \{g^*\}$;

$M \leftarrow M \setminus \{g^*\}$;

end

Definition 2.2.3 (Maximum Nash Welfare). Lastly, there is the Maximum Nash Welfare (MNW), whose objective is to maximize the product of the utilities of the goods, $\prod_i v_i(A_i)$, assigned to the agents. This is sometimes also defined in terms of the geometric mean: $(\prod_{i \in N} v_i(A_i))^{1/n}$. It was proven by Caragiannis et al. (2019b) that this method always leads to an allocation that is not only EF1, but also Pareto optimal. And now, we have just introduced another relevant concept to the topic of fair allocation of goods.

Definition 2.2.4 (Pareto optimality). An allocation A is considered to be Pareto optimal (PO) if there is no allocation B such that $v_i(B_i) \geq v_i(A_i)$ for all agents $i \in N$ and $v_j(B_j) > v_j(A_j)$ for some agent $j \in N$. In other words, there is no other possible allocation by which at least one of the agents will be happier, and none of them will be less happy.

Any Maximum Nash Welfare allocation ensures EF1 and Pareto optimality. However,

computing MNW allocations is not an easy problem, it is NP-hard, Garg et al. (2022), in fact, APX-hard, Barman et al. (2018b). This means, that even finding approximations to MNW allocations is significantly challenging. Although the computation of this type of allocations is still unclear, it has been recently shown by Barman et al. (2018a) that it is possible to achieve EF1 and PO allocations in pseudo-polynomial time.

2.2.2 Envy-freeness up to any good (EFX)

EF1 is a relatively weak notion as it classifies an allocation as fair even when a high-valued good is hypothetically removed from another agent's bundle. Thus, a stronger notion than EF1 is introduced: envy-freeness up to any good, also known, as EFX. It was proposed by Caragiannis et al. (2019b), which stated that an allocation is EFX if for every pair of agents $(i, j) \in N$:

$$v_i(A_i) \geq v_i(A_j \setminus \{g\}) \text{ for any } g \in A_j$$

In other words, an allocation is said to be EFX when the envy from an agent i towards another agent j can be eliminated by taking out any good from j 's bundle.

However, the existence of such allocations has not been proven yet and is indeed one of the biggest open problems related to the fair allocation of goods right now. Consequently, the latest research has been focusing on relaxations of EFX or applying this notion to a small number of agents. As a result, it has been successfully proven that envy-freeness up to any good exists in a certain number of cases.

It was shown by Plaut and Roughgarden (2020) that EFX exists in the case of two agents and that such allocation can be achieved through a 'cut-and-choose'-type protocol. In this procedure, one of the agents creates the two bundles to be assigned following EFX and the other one chooses whichever bundle they prefer. It was later proved by Chaudhury et al. (2020) that EFX is also possible for three agents with complete allocations in pseudo-polynomial time. This was recently improved by a simpler algorithm proposed by Akrami et al. (2023).

The next case in which envy-freeness up to any good is feasible is when agents have identical valuations for the goods. But before delving into this matter, it is pertinent to discuss another relevant concept known as leximin++. The leximin++ maximises the minimum utility, then it maximises the size of the bundle with the minimum value; after that, it continues to maximize the second minimum utility and so on. It was proved by Plaut and Roughgarden (2020) that leximin++ allocation produces not only EFX but also Pareto optimal allocations for identical valuations. However, achieving this type of allocation is NP-hard.

Once again, it was proven by Plaut and Roughgarden (2020) that EFX allocations also exist for ordered valuations through the envy-cycle elimination algorithm in polynomial time. In this case, agents have the exact ordering for goods with possible different values for each of them. Lastly, we are able to obtain EFX allocations with bi-valued instances, in which there are only two possible values for the goods. Amanatidis et al. (2021) showed that EFX allocations were achievable for any number of agents for

bi-valuation instances.

2.2.3 Relaxations of EFX

Given that envy-freeness up to any good is a very strong notion, there exist relaxations of this concept that aim to achieve allocations that are approximately EFX. We define an allocation as α -EFX, being $\alpha \in (0, 1]$, if for every pair of agents $(i, j) \in N$:

$$v_i(A_i) \geq \alpha \cdot v_i(A_j \setminus \{g\}) \text{ for any } g \in A_j$$

Plaut and Roughgarden (2020) demonstrated the existence of 1/2-EFX, which was subsequently proven by Chan et al. (2019) to be achievable in polynomial time. And even more, in the case of additive valuations, the envy-cycle elimination always computes 1/2-EFX allocations, (Chan et al., 2019). More studies have focused on determining the optimal value for α . The best result so far was achieved by Amanatidis et al. (2020), who improved the approximation ratio to 0.618.

Nonetheless, as already mentioned before, it is still a big question in this topic whether or not EFX allocations are possible for more than three agents or if it is possible to improve even more that ratio α . The latest research has been focused on the relaxation of the requirement to allocate all the available goods so that only some goods are left unallocated. There have been important achievements by Caragiannis et al. (2019a) and Chaudhury et al. (2021) on this field, which are further explained in Amanatidis et al. (2022).

2.3 SW, Price of Fairness and Group Fairness

Lastly, there are three more interrelated key concepts that need to be explained: social welfare, price of fairness and group fairness.

Social welfare is defined as the sum of the utilities of the agents for the goods they receive. Thus, the social welfare of an algorithm A is:

$$SW(A) = \sum_{i \in N} v_i(A_i).$$

Ideally, our goal is to maximize this metric. Nevertheless, it is not enough to only maximize social welfare, the allocation also has to follow other notions of fairness like envy-freeness or proportionality. Here is where the concept of price of fairness, defined by Bertsimas et al. (2011) and Caragiannis et al. (2019b), enters the picture. This notion measures the maximum social welfare that can be achieved on an input over the social welfare that the algorithm gets when it is fair. Formally defined, the price of fairness with respect to a fairness criterion F , where $OPT(I)$ is the maximum social welfare that can be achieved over an instance I , is:

$$PoF(F) = \sup_I \min_{A \in F(I)} \frac{OPT(I)}{SW(A)}$$

There are multiple algorithms that aim to achieve the minimum price of fairness for EF1. The first one, designed for only two agents, is a variation of the well-known Adjusted-Winner algorithm by Brams and Taylor (1996). The main idea behind this algorithm is to sort the goods according to the ratios between the values for both agents, in the following way:

$$\frac{v_1(g_1)}{v_2(g_1)} > \frac{v_1(g_2)}{v_2(g_2)} > \dots > \frac{v_1(g_m)}{v_2(g_m)}$$

It was proved by Bei et al. (2021) that assigning a minimal set of consecutive goods from the left to the first agent, ensuring an EF1 allocation for them, and assigning the rest of the goods to the second agent, results in an EF1 allocation with social welfare within a $\sqrt{3}/2$ -fraction of the optimal social welfare.

Algorithm 3: Minimum Price of Fairness (Min-PoF) Algorithm for 2 agents

Input: A fair allocation instance $I = (N, M, v)$ with (n) agents and m goods.

Output: Allocation $A = (A_1, \dots, A_n)$.

```

for each agent  $i \in N$  do
  |  $A_i \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
end
for each good  $j \in N$  do
  |  $r_j \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
end
for each good  $j \in M$  do
  |  $r[j] \leftarrow v[0][j] / v[1][j]$ 
end
Sort goods according to ratio in descending order
for each good  $j \in r$  do
  | repeat
  | |  $A_1 \leftarrow \text{ratio}[j]$ 
  | |  $A_2 \leftarrow \text{elements remaining in ratio}$ 
  | until
  |  $\text{EF1 allocation for the first agent}$ 
end

```

However, this last algorithm is only for two agents. Barman et al. (2020) managed to give an upper bound of the price of fairness for EF1 for n -arbitrary agents of $O(\sqrt{n})$. In this paper, it is included an algorithm for n -arbitrary agents that is also designed to obtain the minimal price of fairness for EF1. This algorithm manages to produce an EF1 allocation with social welfare:

$$SW(A) \geq \frac{OPT}{12/\sqrt{n}} - \frac{1}{6}$$

The first step of this algorithm is to obtain a reference allocation W^* with optimal social welfare. This algorithm was originally designed for subadditive valuations, for which

finding such allocation is NP-hard (Dobzinski et al., 2005). Therefore, Barman et al. (2020) had to use Feige’s algorithm to get an allocation with a 2-approximation to the optimal social welfare.

Nonetheless, throughout this dissertation, we worked under the assumption of additive valuations for which it is possible to obtain an allocation with optimal social welfare. Thus, we slightly modified the algorithm in order to cover this change.

Algorithm 4: Minimum Price of Fairness (Min-PoF) for n-arbitrary agents

Input: A fair allocation instance $I = (N, M, v)$ with (n) agents and m goods.

Output: An EF1 Allocation $A = (A_1, \dots, A_n)$ with social welfare

$$SW(A) \geq \frac{OPT}{12/\sqrt{n}} - \frac{1}{6}.$$

Compute an allocation W with maximum social welfare.

Re-index the goods as $\{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_m\}$ such that they have each W_i forms a connected subgraph in the line graph L over the goods.

for each agent $i \in N$ **do**

if $W_i = \emptyset$ **then**

$P_i = \emptyset$

else

 pick $g_i^* \in \arg \max_{g \in W_i} v_i(g)$ and set $P_i = g_i^*$

end

while for some agent i , $v_i(P_i) < v(U)$ being U an unassigned connected bundle in L

do

 Let U be the set of goods $\{g_a, g_{a+1}, \dots, g_b\}$

 Pick the minimum $c \in [a, b]$ such that $v_k(P_k) < v_k(\{g_a, g_{a+1}, \dots, g_c\})$ for some $k \in [n]$

 Pick an arbitrary agent k for which $v_k(P_k) < v_k(\{g_a, g_{a+1}, \dots, g_c\})$

 Append to the partial allocation P_k the subset $\{g_a, g_{a+1}, \dots, g_c\}$

end

Use envy-cycle elimination algorithm to extend the EF1 partial allocation to a complete EF1 allocation A such that $v_i(A_i) \leq v_i(P_i)$ for each $i \in [n]$.

Once we have obtained this optimal welfare allocation, the next step is to index the goods as g_1, g_2, \dots, g_m such that for each W_i the goods receive consecutive indices. This is the same as each of the W_i forming a connected subgraph of L ; let L be the line graph that is formed with all the goods. After this, the algorithm creates a partial allocation P_i , in which each agent i that received a good in the reference allocation W_i , is given their most valued good from W_i . Every time an agent receives a good, that good will be removed from the line graph L .

Hereunder, we check if there is any agent that values more any of the remaining connected components in the line graph L than their own allocation. If this is true for multiple agents, we randomly pick one and assign them the minimal subset of that envied connected bundle that satisfies the condition. We continue doing this until there is no agent that values more one of the assigned connected bundles than their own allocation. Nevertheless, at this point, there might still be goods that have not yet been

assigned. To expand this partial EF1 allocation, the algorithm executes envy-cycle elimination resulting in an EF1 allocation as the final outcome.

Finally, there is the concept of group fairness. While our previous focus has been on individual fairness, there are instances in which the priority is to achieve group fairness. An allocation is said to be group-fair when it is not possible to redistribute the goods allocated to one group amongst the other group so that all the members of the latest group are happier.

2.4 Related work

Although not the primary focus of this dissertation, there are additional relevant concepts related to the fair allocation of indivisible goods.

2.4.1 Proportionality(Prop)

This is one of the notions directly related to the concept of ‘fairness’. As well as envy-freeness, relaxations for proportionality exist, being the main one Prop1.

Prop1: Proportionality up to one good (Prop1) was introduced by Conitzer et al. (2017) who established that an allocation is Prop1 if for every agent $i \in N$, there exists a good $g \in M$, such that:

$$v_i(A_i \cup \{g\}) \geq \frac{v_i(M)}{n}$$

In other words, each agent should be able to get their proportional share of the total by giving them an extra good.

2.4.2 MMS

Another key notion that must be introduced is the Maximin Share (MMS) which is defined as:

$$MMS_i^k(S) = \max_{(P_1, \dots, P_k) \in \Pi_k(S)} \min_{1 \leq j \leq k} v_i(P_j)$$

The maximin share fair answers the question of what is the maximum utility that an agent can assure for themselves when they are the ones creating the bundles but they get the worst one. An allocation will be considered MMS when:

$$v_i(A_i) = MMS_i^n(M)$$

Even though MMS is a desirable notion, Procaccia and Wang (2014) established that there are instances for which MMS allocations do not exist.

2.4.3 Chore division

There is a relevant line of research in the field that focuses on the fair allocations of chores, this can be considered as goods that are negatively valued by the agents.

While the EF definition remains unchanged, its relaxations require some modifications to capture these negative valuations. In this scenario, rather than removing goods from other agents' bundles to eliminate the envy of an agent, we aim to remove chores from that agent's bundle themselves. An allocation A is considered to be α -EF1 if for any pair of agents i, j and some $g \in A_i$:

$$v_i(A_i \setminus \{g\}) \geq \alpha \cdot v_i(A_j)$$

The allocation A is considered to be α -EFX if the inequality holds for any $g \in A_i$.

Chapter 3

Implementation

3.1 Structure of the code

The code is divided into six main classes: four focused on the implementation of the relevant algorithms (Round-Robin, Envy-cycle elimination and Minimum Price of Fairness for two and n-arbitrary agents) and then two for the computation of metrics.

There are some common data structures for all the algorithms. Both agents and goods are lists of integer values. For the valuations and allocations, we used dictionaries:

- Valuations dictionary: the keys are the agents' identifiers and the value is another dictionary in which the key is the good identifier, and the value is the valuation of that specific good.
- Allocation dictionary: the keys are the agents' identifiers and the value is a list containing the goods received by an agent.

3.1.1 Round-Robin class

The first class implements the Round-Robin algorithm. Given that we need to update the list of available goods for each round, a copy of the list of goods is created with the goal of not modifying the original data.

3.1.2 Envy-cycle Elimination class

Next, is the class focused on Envy-cycle elimination, a more complex algorithm that requires multiple help functions for its implementation. ECE, as it was previously explained in definition 2.2.2, works with graphs in which the nodes represent the agents, and the edges are the envy between the agents. In the implementation, in order to keep track of these envies, instead of using a graph structure, we use a dictionary where the key is an agent, and the value is a list of the agents envied by the key. This dictionary is also used to find the agents that are not envied, what we call 'sources', which is a key step of the algorithm.

Even though it might seem like a trivial task, one of the main challenges during the implementation of ECE was to check whether there was a cycle and, if so, solve it. In order to determine the existence of a cycle, we use depth-first search (DFS)¹. There are two functions that handle this step:

- *check_cycle_util*: recursive function in charge of the exploration of the graph, in our case, the dictionary of envied agents. It keeps track of the visited nodes (agents), maintains a path variable to be able to reconstruct the cycle if found, and also uses a stack to identify back edges which indicate a cycle. An edge is considered a ‘back edge’ if it leads from a visited node to a node that has already been visited.
- *check_cycle*: function that manages the overall process, iterating through the non-visited nodes.

In regards to solving the cycle, once the agents that form it have been identified, we just rotate their bundles. To do this, a copy of the original allocation is needed, so we are able to access all the required data and we do not modify it during the rotation.

We also implemented two variations of the Envy-cycle elimination:

- 1st variant: when there are agents that are not envied, instead of choosing one of them randomly, the algorithm prioritises those ones that have not received any good yet.
- 2nd variant: the algorithm takes a partial allocation as input and expands it to a complete allocation, but the core algorithm logic remains the same.

3.1.3 Minimum Price of Fairness for two agents class

Then, there is the Minimum Price of Fairness algorithm for two agents. In this class, we make use of a dictionary to store the ratio between the valuations of both agents for a specific good.

3.1.4 Minimum Price of Fairness for n-arbitrary agents class

For the Minimum Price of Fairness for n-arbitrary agents, we encountered certain challenges. The major challenge was the representation and handling of the line graph the algorithm uses. To achieve this, we used a list of lists structure. Each of the sublists represents a connected subgraph of the line graph. This data structure is used to determine whether there is any agent that values a subgraph more than their own bundle. Moreover, this algorithm is the one that utilizes the variation for partial allocations of the Envy-cycle Elimination.

¹The depth-first search explores a graph as deeply as possible along each branch and then it backtracks to explore other branches (Holzmann et al., 1996)

3.1.5 Fairness and evaluation metrics classes

The last two main classes, as previously mentioned, are in charge of computing the metrics. One of them focuses on the fairness metrics so it has the necessary functions to check if an allocation is EF, EF1, EFX or α -EFX. To calculate this, a complementary method was needed that determined the total value of an allocation for an agent. On the other hand, the second class is responsible for computing the price of fairness and social welfare achieved by an allocation. Here, we also include a method to evaluate the maximum possible social welfare for a given instance.

3.1.6 Auxiliary classes

In addition to the classes defined in the previous sections, there are two auxiliary classes related to the experiments. The first one focuses on the generation of the data from mathematical distributions - this will be further explained in the next section. We also include in this class the required methods to create and save the results from the experiments in `.csv` files. The final class is for the execution of the experiments themselves and the specification of the parameters.

A visual representation of the code implementation can be observed in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Flowchart of the code structure

Chapter 4

Experiments

4.1 Data

The experiments of this project focus on the characteristics of the allocations calculated by multiple algorithms. For their computation, the required data is a list of agents and goods and the corresponding valuations of the goods by the participating agents. We obtain this data through two different sources: the Spliddit website and data generated from mathematical distributions.

4.1.1 Spliddit data

Spliddit.org is a website that aims to help with fair division problems, offering multiple tools for fair resource allocation. This platform allows users to split credit, bills, chores, or material items between people. In addition to these fair division calculators, the website also provides negotiation facilitators so that all parties can reach a beneficial agreement when dividing the resources (Shah, 2017).

The algorithms used by Spliddit are based on the principles of fairness and efficiency. The allocations created by the platform have to satisfy multiple criteria, such as envy-freeness or proportionality (Shah, 2017).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	204	124	160	189	101	117	105	
2	140	94	71	262	122	183	128	
3	244	128	74	261	92	61	140	
4								
5								

Figure 4.1: Screenshot of Instance 17 from Spliddit data. Each row represents an agent, each column a good and each cell contains the valuation of a good from an agent.

In order to compute the allocations, the website needs the users to provide their valuations of the goods or tasks that are going to be distributed. We were able to access a portion of these valuations and use them for our experiments. The obtained data contained more than two thousand instances, each of them containing the valuations of

multiple goods from different agents. The number of agents was within a range from 3 to 15, and the number of goods went from 2 to 85. In Figure 4.1, we can observe an example of an instance with seven goods to distribute among three agents. The use of this real data is essential for practical applications, as it accurately captures individual preferences and behaviours.

4.1.2 Generated data

Nonetheless, despite the relevance of the Spliddit material, it is also convenient to generate our own data. This enables us to have more control over the experiment set-up and the properties of the data itself. This is key so we can perform more focalised experiments. Even though the Spliddit data has instances with a variety of number of agents and goods, it would be interesting to analyse how the algorithms behave when allocating a much larger number of goods. For this reason, when generating the data, we have considered up to a thousand goods to distribute among the agents.

The data is drawn from three mathematical distributions: uniform, normal, and beta.

- Uniform distribution: distribution for which all outcomes are equally likely. This can be visualized as a straight horizontal line as observed in Figure 4.2a. This distribution is defined by its minimum and maximum values, in our case, 0 and 1 (Dekking, 2005, p. 60).
- Normal distribution: also known as the Gaussian distribution, is represented by a bell-shaped curve symmetric about the mean (Berger and Casella, 2001) as shown in Figure 4.2b. This intuitively implies that the data near the mean will be more frequent than the one far from the mean. The mean (μ) and the standard deviation (σ) are 0.5 for our experiments.
- Beta distribution: distribution defined on the interval $[0, 1]$. Its shape depends on its two parameters: alpha (α) and beta (β) (Johnson et al., 1995, Chapter 25). We use $\alpha = 0.05$ and $\beta = 0.1$ for the experiments.

Figure 4.2: Visualization of distributions.

Initially, our decision to draw data from three distinct distributions was driven by an interest in exploring any potential difference in the algorithms' behaviour across different data. However, after further analysis, we concluded that the use of one

distribution or another did not significantly impact the outcomes of the experiments. As a result, we decided only to utilize the normal distribution for our experiments.

4.2 Experiments set-up

For the performed experiments, we use three configurations depending on the specific features we want to analyse. For each of the instances, we compute whether the allocation is EF1, EFX, and/or EF. We also calculate their social welfare, price of fairness, and the algorithm runtime.

4.2.1 Set-up 1

In this set-up, the 2309 instances of the Spliddit data are used. The allocations are computed by one of these three algorithms: Round-Robin, Envy-cycle elimination, or Minimum Price of Fairness. Given the diverse range of agent counts in the Spliddit data, we do not use the Minimum Price of Fairness for two agents, opting instead for the version designed for an arbitrary number of agents.

4.2.2 Set-up 2

For this second configuration, the data is generated through a normal distribution. We keep a constant number of agents; for this set-up case, we use two agents and vary the number of goods. As it is of special interest to observe the behaviour of algorithms for an increasing number of goods, we perform the experiments with 10, 20, 100, 500 and 1000 goods. For each number of goods, 1000 instances are generated. This specific set-up enables us to analyse the behaviour of the Min-PoF for two agents, which we were not able to study with the Spliddit data. Not only that but it can also be compared with the other two algorithms, RR and ECE.

4.2.3 Set-up 3

In this final configuration, the data is, once again, obtained from a normal distribution. The number of agents remains constant, for this set-up, it is 10 agents. We use an increasing number of goods, doing the experiments with 10, 20, 100, 500 and 1000 goods. As in the previous set-up, we generate 1000 instances for each number of goods. The algorithms that are used to compute the allocations are: RR, ECE and Min-PoF for n-arbitrary agents.

4.3 Experiments to analyse fairness metrics

The execution of experiments to analyse the fairness metrics of the algorithms is key to understand their behaviour and performance. The fairness metrics under consideration include the percentage of envy-free (EF), envy-free up to one good (EF1), and envy-free up to any good (EFX) allocations. Given that envy-freeness is one of the criteria that qualifies an allocation as 'fair', conducting these experiments is justified.

4.3.1 Evaluation of RR for fairness metrics with Spliddit data

In this experiment, we utilize set-up 1 (Section 4.2.1), which incorporates the Spliddit data. From the 2309 allocations generated by Round-Robin, we compute the number of EF1, EFX and EF allocations. We shall recall that RR is an algorithm designed to consistently produce EF1 allocations; thus, we anticipate obtaining a 100% rate of such allocations.

Results

Following the analysis of the outcomes, we obtain that out of the total number of allocations, 1528 were EFX, which represents 66.18% of the total. Regarding the envy-freeness metric, 772 were EF, a 33.42%. As envy-freeness is a stricter constraint, it is reasonable that its percentage is lower as it implies that no agent on the system is envious. Additionally, considering that Round-Robin is a straightforward algorithm that does not consider the envy among agents and that distributes goods uniquely based on their valuations, it is logical that these results are not optimal.

Expansion

After a more detailed examination of the results, we detect that instances where the number of goods is not divisible by the number of agents are less likely to result in EF or EFX allocations. To check the validity of our hypothesis, we categorise the instances into two groups. One of the groups includes the instances in which the number of goods is divisible by the number of agents, with a total of 2059 instances. The other group consists of the non-divisible ones, totalling 250 instances.

Results of the expansion

In the first group - instances where the number of goods is a multiple of the number of agents - we obtain 1382 EFX allocations (67.09%) and 731 EF allocations (58.40%). For the second group, the algorithm achieves 146 EFX allocations (35.49%) and 41 EF ones (16.4%). It is evident that the divisibility significantly impacts the fairness of the allocations, as instances from the first group exhibit higher percentages for both EFX and EF allocations, as shown in Table 4.1

When the number of goods is divisible by the number of agents, all agents receive the same number of goods, reducing the likelihood of envy among them. Nevertheless, in the opposite case, at least one agent receives fewer goods than the rest, leading to a higher probability of envy.

	All instances	Goods divisible by agents	Goods not divisible by agents
% EF1	100.00	100.00	100.00
% EFX	66.18	67.09	58.40
% EF	33.42	35.49	16.4

Table 4.1: Percentages of EF1, EFX and EF allocations with Round-Robin.

Conclusions

Despite not achieving optimal outcomes, Round-Robin's capacity to generate EFX allocations in over half the instances is satisfactory, particularly given that EFX's

existence has not yet been proven. The lower percentage of EF allocations compared to EFX is logical, considering that EF is a stronger notion. Furthermore, in cases where the number of goods is not a multiple of the number of agents, a significant decrease in the percentage of EFX and EF allocations is observed, with the latter experiencing a particularly notable decline.

Further research: Calculation of α -EFX for RR.

We have just stated that out of the 2309 analysed instances, the Round-Robin algorithm produced 1528 EFX allocations. Nevertheless, this also implies there are 781 allocations that do not meet the EFX criterion. Our next step is to analyse whether these allocations can be approximately EFX, denoted as α -EFX. For each of these non-EFX allocations, we calculate the highest possible α - where $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ - that ensures the allocation being α -EFX. After the computation of these individual alphas, we identify the maximum α that guarantees all allocations are α -EFX.

Results:

Following the calculation of alphas for each allocation and thorough analysis of the results, we encounter an unexpected issue. There are 249 instances for which we obtain that the maximum α value is 0.0. This is exemplified by the following sample:

Example 4.3.1. This instance presents the problem of distributing six goods among three agents:

	Good a	Good b	Good c	Good d	Good e	Good f
Agent 1	0	0	0	0	0	1000
Agent 2	87	292	135	225	72	189
Agent 3	87	211	143	103	145	311

Table 4.2: Agents' valuations for available goods.

The allocation generated by RR for this scenario is as follows: agent 1 receives goods a and c ; agent 2 receives goods b and d ; and agent 3 receives goods e and f . The problem lies on the fact that agent 1 only values good f and does not value any of the other goods. This implies that the only situation in which agent 1 is not envious is if they receive this specific good. However, as we have just stated, good f is not assigned to agent 1.

This allocation is qualified as EF1 since the only envious agent is agent 1, and that envy can be eliminated by removing good f from agent 3. However, when analysing whether the allocation satisfies the EFX criterion, it is evident that it does not. It is not enough to remove any good from agent 3 to eliminate the envy from agent 1, it specifically requires the removal of good f . Since an allocation is only considered EFX when envy disappears with the removal of any good, we have just established that this allocation is not EFX.

Regarding α -EFX, we need to find an α for which the valuation of agent 1 of their own bundle is larger than or equal to the valuation of agent 1 of agent 3's bundle. This translates to the inequality: $0 \geq \alpha 1000$. For this equation to hold true, α must be 0.00.

Heuristic:

Considering that the experiment aims to determine the maximum α that ensures all instances being α -EFX, such instances do not facilitate the determination of meaningful outcomes. Hence, a heuristic directly related to the order in which goods are distributed is employed to improve the results of Round-Robin.

For every instance where we find $\alpha = 0.00$, we identify the agents or agents which are leading to this result. After that, we prioritise these agents during good distribution, allowing them to select first, with the objective of potentially reducing their envy on the final allocation.

After the application of the heuristic, improved results are achieved. Out of the initial 249 instances for which the computed α was 0.00, the implementation of the new heuristic reduces this number to 191. This indicates that for 58 instances, we managed to obtain an alpha value different from 0. Even for some cases, the newly calculated alpha is 1, implying that the heuristic successfully converted the allocations to meet the EFX criterion. This represents a significant finding: while any ordering of agents in RR produces EF1 allocations, altering the ordering could elevate the allocation from 0-EFX to EFX.

Nonetheless, there are still 191 instances for which alpha is 0.00. This is the case in the following instance:

Example 4.3.2. Here, we present a scenario involving three agents and six goods available for distribution among them:

	Good a	Good b	Good c	Good d	Good e	Good f
Agent 1	1000	0	0	0	0	0
Agent 2	10000	0	0	0	0	0
Agent 3	995	5	0	0	0	0

Table 4.3: Agents' valuations for available goods.

In the original allocation - before the application of the heuristic - agent 1 receives goods *c* and *f*; agent 2 is assigned goods *a* and *d*; and agent 3 is allocated goods *b* and *e*. This scenario presents a challenge as agents 1 and 3 only value good *a* and do not value the other goods at all. Agent 3, although valuing good *b* to some extent, most of their valuation relies on good *a*. Since agent 2 receives good *a*, the other two agents envy them, and therefore, it becomes evident that the only suitable alpha for this case is $\alpha = 0.00$.

Following the application of the heuristic, the new allocations for this instance are as follows: agent 1 receives goods *a* and *d*; agent 2 is allocated goods *b* and *e*; and agent 3 is assigned goods *c* and *f*. We observe that, as agent 1 is one of the agents that contributed to the previous 0-EFX allocation, it is now the first one to select a good. However, despite this adjustment, the allocation still does not satisfy the α -EFX criterion. There is no $\alpha \neq 0$ that could be multiplied by agent 2's valuation of agent 1's bundle to ensure that it is less than or equal to agent 2's valuation of their own bundle.

In fact, the only viable approach so that this allocation, or similar ones, are EFX would be to uniquely assign good a to agent 1 . In this scenario, since agent 1 only possesses one good, the envy from the other agents would disappear regardless of which good is removed from agent 1 's bundle. Nevertheless, this would deviate from the Round-Robin algorithm that distributes goods following an arbitrary order that remains unaffected by the envy of the system.

Final results:

With the objective of obtaining meaningful results concerning the notion of α -EFX, extreme cases like Example 4.3.2 are disregarded. Instead, we focus on examining the 532 instances that were originally α -EFX and the 58 that are α -EFX after the employment of the heuristic.

Figure 4.3: Frequency of alpha values produced with the Round-Robin algorithm for α -EFX allocations.

The computed alphas range from $[0.1, 1]$. In Figure 4.3, there is a noticeable variation in frequency across different α values, with peaks observed at certain points, particularly at $\alpha = 0.99$, where there are 25 instances. This peak suggests that these instances are very close to achieving the envy-freeness up to any good. Another point of interest is the analysis of the percentage of α values that are ≥ 0.618 , which stands as the best theoretical EFX approximation guarantee (Amanatidis et al., 2020). We obtained satisfactory outcomes with 330 instances meeting this criterion, which represents 55.93% of the analysed instances that surpassed the theoretical benchmark.

Regarding the maximum α required to ensure that all allocations are α -EFX, it is 0.01, a relatively low value. While this value might not be optimal, given the strong notion of

EFX and the large sample size of over 2300 instances, achieving EFX for all allocations is a notably challenging task.

Conclusions:

This experiment clearly demonstrates the significant impact that the application of a simple heuristic has on the allocations generated by RR, with some instances transitioning from 0-EFX to EFX. However, it also highlights the presence of instances with extreme valuations, where regardless of the adjustment of the good distribution order, RR algorithm fails to produce α -EFX allocations. This emphasizes the notable challenge in achieving α -EFX allocations, as even after excluding these extreme cases, the maximum α value ensuring all allocations are alpha-EFX is 0.01. Nevertheless, Round-Robin demonstrates a satisfactory performance, obtaining an α that exceeds the theoretical EFX approximation guarantee in more than half of the instances.

4.3.2 Evaluation of ECE for fairness metrics with Spliddit data

As in the previous scenario, set-up 1 (Section 4.2.1) is employed for the execution of this experiment. It is important to note that Envy-cycle elimination, like RR, consistently leads to EF1 allocations; therefore, we expect all 2309 computed allocations to be EF1. However, our primary interest is the analysis of the algorithm's performance concerning the other two fairness metrics: EFX and EF. Additionally, given our previous findings that the divisibility of the number of goods by the number of agents has a significant impact on the results, we once again, categorize the data into two subgroups to investigate if a similar pattern emerges with ECE as it did with RR.

Results

As anticipated, all the obtained allocations are EF1. When examining all instances, the results revealed a significant improvement in the proportion of EFX allocations when using ECE, reaching 85.30%. This is nearly 20% more than the percentage achieved by RR. These results are understandable, given that ECE is designed to keep track of envy among agents and distribute the goods accordingly. On the contrary, RR follows an arbitrary order for good distribution that remains unaffected by agents' envy. Surprisingly, however, RR outperforms ECE in the computation of EF allocations, obtaining almost 10% more.

Similar to the previous experiment, we reaffirm the influence of the divisibility of the number of goods by the number of agents on the percentages of EFX and EF allocations. ECE shows similar behaviour to RR, with a higher percentage of EF allocations under divisibility conditions as shown in Table 4.4. Nonetheless, for the EFX allocations, the opposite trend is observed, with a lower percentage when the divisibility constraint is met.

Conclusions

The Envy-cycle Elimination algorithm demonstrates promising results, particularly in the computation of EFX allocations, with a significantly high percentage achieved. Furthermore, the obtained outcomes highlight the influence of the divisibility of the number of goods by the number of agents on the final allocations, with significantly

	All instances	Goods divisible by agents	Goods not divisible by agents
% EF1	100.00	100.00	100.00
% EFX	85.30	83.10	91.2
% EF	26.50	27.60	14.80

Table 4.4: Percentages of EF1, EFX and EF allocations with Envy-Cycle Elimination.

improved results for EF allocations when divisibility is present. Notably, ECE diverges from the previously observed trend, showing a reduction in the percentage of EFX allocations when divisibility conditions are met.

Further research: Calculation of α -EFX for ECE.

ECE successfully generated 1971 EFX allocations, a highly satisfactory result. Nonetheless, there are still 338 allocations that did not meet the EFX criterion. Similar to our approach for RR, our aim now is to analyse if these allocations can be α -EFX. For each of these non-EFX allocations, we calculate the maximum alpha that ensures the allocation is α -EFX. The final goal is to determine the maximum alpha that makes all allocations EFX.

Results:

Among the 338 allocations that are not EFX, the calculated α value is 0.00 for 95 of them, a significantly lower number compared to Round-Robin, which resulted in nearly 250 instances with $\alpha = 0.00$. These differences emphasize the variations in implementations of RR and ECE, with the latter considering envy among agents with the goal of reducing the envy of the overall system.

We provide here an illustrative example of the type of instance that causes ECE to generate 0-EFX allocations:

Example 4.3.3. This presents a scenario involving three agents and six goods available for distribution among them:

	Good a	Good b	Good c	Good d	Good e	Good f
Agent 1	462	0	538	0	0	0
Agent 2	0	0	0	556	444	0
Agent 3	0	5	0	0	0	1000

Table 4.5: Agents' valuations for available goods.

The allocation generated by ECE is as follows: agent 1 receives goods c , a , b and d in that order; agent 2 does not receive any goods; and agent 3 receives goods f and e . With this allocation, agent 2 is envious of agents 1 and 3 and this envy can only be eliminated by removing specifically good d from agent 1, and good e from agent 2.

The issue arises from the random selection step of ECE, where it randomly chooses an agent from the non-envied ones for the distribution of a good. For the presented scenario, during the first round, agent 1 receives good c , and because the other two agents do not value this good, agent 1 remains classified as a non-envied agent. Consequently, in the

next round, agent 1 is randomly selected again and receives good a . This logic continues with good b , and it only changes when agent 1 receives good d . Since this good is also valued by agent 2, an envy situation arises. Therefore, in the next round, there is a random selection between agents 2 and 3 - the non-envied agents - resulting in agent 3 receiving good f . As good f is not valued by anyone else, agent 3 is still categorised as a non-envied agent. In the following round, agent 3 is once again selected and receives good e . This concludes the allocation, leaving agent 2 with an empty bundle. It is not difficult to see that this is a 0-EFX allocation.

Heuristic:

To improve upon these results, we implement a modification of ECE where, when selecting an unenvied agent, we favour agents with empty bundles. Additionally, we employ the heuristic previously used with Round-Robin, slightly modifying the distribution order to prioritise agents that lead to the 0-EFX allocation.

Following the implementation of the heuristic, significantly improved results are obtained, as we manage to get an $\alpha > 0$ for all instances. This represents a notable advancement, especially when compared with Round-Robin, where even with the application of the heuristic, it still generated 191 instances with $\alpha = 0$.

Figure 4.4: Frequency of alpha values produced with the Envy-cycle Elimination algorithm for α -EFX allocations.

Final results: The calculated alphas resulting from ECE and the heuristic implementation, range from $[0.1, 1]$. In Figure 4.4, a notable spike is evident for $\alpha = 1.00$, with 92 instances that transition from 0-EFX to EFX after the application of the heuristic. Recall that 0.618 is the best theoretical EFX approximation guarantee. Among the 338 instances that initially were not EFX, 301 exhibit an $\alpha > 0.618$; this represents 89.05%

of the instances. These outcomes are highly satisfactory, affirming ECE's efficacy in computing allocations with reduced envy.

Concerning the required α for achieving α -EFX for all instances, it is 0.01. However, only one instance presents this α value; most other instances, as shown in Figure 4.4, have significantly higher alpha values.

Conclusions:

In line with previous experiments, we confirm the notable impact of a simple heuristic on outcomes. The application of this heuristic to ECE resulted in the transformation of 92 instances that originally were 0-EFX to EFX allocations. These satisfactory results emphasized the superior performance of ECE compared to RR regarding EFX allocations. This is logical as ECE systematically monitors envy within the system and distributes goods accordingly. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that almost 90% of the instances achieved an α superior to the theoretical EFX approximation guarantee.

4.3.3 Evaluation of modification of ECE for fairness metrics with Spliddit data

For this experiment, we employ set-up 1 (Section 4.2.1). Here, we analyse a variant of the previously used Envy-cycle Elimination. The algorithm's description does not specify whether it checks for cycles after the allocation of all goods. In Experiment 4.3.2, we utilized the standard version, which does not check for cycles at the end. Nevertheless, in this version, we do check for cycles after distributing the last good; if a cycle is detected, the goods are rearranged to break it. Since cycles tend to reduce the overall envy within the system, we expect to obtain improved outcomes concerning the percentages of EFX and EF allocations.

Results

Out of the 2309 instances, using this modification of the algorithm, we obtained 1947 allocations that are EFX and 670 that meet the EF criterion. As observed in Table 4.6, there is a noticeable improvement in the percentages of EFX and EF allocations compared to the version of ECE that does not address cycles at the end. The enhancement is particularly significant for the EF notion, showing a 2.5% improvement. The change in EFX allocations is relatively minor, with an increase of less than 0.2%. It is logical that the impact on EF allocations is more notable; if a cycle involving all agents is detected and solved, there is a high probability of obtaining an envy-free allocation as all agents are receiving the bundle they envy. These findings validate our initial hypothesis: checking for cycles does indeed reduce the overall envy of the system, thereby increasing the likelihood of generating an EFX or EF allocation.

Conclusions

The variant of the Envy-cycle Elimination has proved to exhibit superior performance in generating EF and EFX allocations with a particular improvement observed in the percentage of EF allocations.

	Solving cycles at the end	Not solving cycles at the end
% EF1	100.00	100.00
% EFX	84.22	84.06
% EF	29.0	26.50

Table 4.6: Comparison of percentages of EF1, EFX and EF allocations with the original and the modified Envy-Cycle Elimination.

4.3.4 Evaluation of Min-PoF for fairness metrics with Spliddit data

For this experiment, we employ set-up 1 (Section 4.2.1), incorporating all the Spliddit data which includes diverse scenarios involving varying numbers of goods and agents. To address this diversity, we use the version of Minimum Price of Fairness that is designed for n -arbitrary agents. As in previous experiments, we aim to analyse the behaviour of this algorithm and evaluate its performance concerning fairness metrics. Consistent with our last experiments, we categorize the Spliddit instances into two groups depending on the divisibility of the number of goods over the number of agents.

Results

This algorithm is designed to consistently generate EF1 allocations, which is confirmed by all the produced allocations meeting this criterion. Regarding the other two fairness metrics, when considering all the instances, this algorithm obtained the highest number of EFX allocations - out of the 2309 instances, 2068 were EFX. This outcome is understandable, given that the implementation of this method includes the ECE for partial allocations in its final step. As previously explained, the ECE takes into account the agent's envy for the good distribution, thus it is reasonable that the use of Min-PoF leads to satisfactory results regarding EFX allocations. On the contrary, the percentage of EF allocations was significantly lower, only 28.94%.

	All instances	Goods divisible by agents	Goods not divisible by agents
% EF1	100.00	100.00	100.00
% EFX	89.50	89.20	92.00
% EF	28.94	30.02	18.00

Table 4.7: Percentages of EF1, EFX and EF allocations with Min-PoF for n -arbitrary agents.

When dividing the instances into two groups, even though the percentage of EFX allocations remains relatively unaffected, the percentage of EF allocations significantly decreases when the number of goods is not divisible by the number of agents. This aligns with previous findings regarding how the percentage of EF is affected by this divisibility. It reflects the intuitive notion that if all agents receive the same number of goods, there is a higher possibility of reducing envy among them.

Conclusions

The Minimum Price of Fairness for n -arbitrary agents outperforms the other analysed algorithms, achieving the highest number of EFX allocations. This success can be

attributed to its implementation, which includes the use of ECE. Additionally, while the divisibility of the number of times by the number of agents has minimal impact on the percentage of EFX allocations, the number of EF allocations experiences a notable decrease when divisibility is not maintained. Overall, the algorithm shows good performance when generating EFX allocations.

In Figure 4.5 we present the findings of Experiments 4.3.1, 4.3.2 and 4.3.4 more visually.

Figure 4.5: Comparison of the percentages of EF, EF1 and EFX allocations by different algorithms.

4.3.5 Evaluation of RR, ECE, Min-PoF for fairness metrics with generated data

For the conduction of this experiment, we make use of set-up 2 (Section 4.2.2) and set-up 3 (Section 4.2.3). In preceding experiments, we analysed the fairness metrics for three of the studied algorithms (RR, ECE and Min-PoF for n -arbitrary agents) utilizing the Spliddit data as the experimental configuration.

With the aim of also evaluating the performance of the Min-PoF for 2 agents algorithm, we employ generated data with a fixed number of agents at 2 (set-up 2) and an increasing number of goods. Additionally, to observe how the previously analysed three algorithms perform in a similar scenario, we used set-up 3, which maintains a constant number of agents at 10.

Results

The outcomes of the experiment, shown in Tables 4.8 and 4.9, reveal a clear pattern across most algorithms: as the number of goods increases, the percentages of EF and

EFX allocations also grow. Additionally, as all these algorithms are designed to achieve EF1 allocations, and they indeed accomplished this goal, we found it unnecessary to incorporate these values in the results tables.

Round-Robin: It emerges as the algorithm that exhibits better performance in both scenarios. However, despite the highly satisfactory results, it is evident that the number of agents significantly impacts these fairness metrics. When handling only two agents, this algorithm achieves perfect or almost-perfect scores for both EF and EFX metrics, as evidenced in Table 4.8. Concerning the case of ten agents, optimal values are maintained for 100, 500 and 1000 goods. When handling 20 goods, while the EFX percentage remains notably high, there is a significant dropout in the EF percentage.

This suggests that the closer the number of agents and goods are, the more the percentages of the fairness metrics decrease. Conversely, with a greater number of goods to distribute among a few agents, there is a higher likelihood of each agent obtaining their desired goods without envying others. This emphasizes the importance of flexibility during the distribution of the goods, which enhances the likelihood of achieving satisfactory allocations for the agents.

algorithm		Fairness percentages				
		10 goods	20 goods	100 goods	500 goods	1000 goods
Round-Robin	%EF	98.0	100	100	100	100
	%EFX	99.5	100	100	100	100
ECE	%EF	87.6	96.1	100	100	100
	%EFX	95.5	98.0	100	100	100
Min-PoF	%EF	41.9	43.3	35.6	32.3	32.1
	%EFX	53.3	48.5	36.3	32.3	32.3

Table 4.8: Fairness metrics when handling 2 agents.

Envy-cycle elimination: This algorithm demonstrates a similar behaviour to RR, although with slightly inferior results, particularly when managing 10 agents. For instance, the percentage of EF allocations with 10 agents and 20 goods is extremely low, only 0.8%. The EFX percentage stands at 43.2% - fifty per cent lower than the results achieved by RR. Nevertheless, we observe once again that as the number of goods increases, the envy-freeness of the allocations also improves, reaching optimal values for 1000 goods.

Despite ECE being an algorithm that constantly considers agents' envy and tries to minimize it whenever possible, it fails to produce better results than the simple Round-Robin algorithm.

Minimum Price of Fairness for 2 agents: It consistently achieves the lowest fairness scores across all number of goods among the four methods analysed. Contrary to the previously observed trend, the percentages of EF and EFX allocations decrease as the number of goods grows. This deviation originates from the algorithm's prioritization of allocating goods to the first agent based on their valuation ratio, and only after, considering the remaining goods for the second agent. Consequently, with an increasing number of goods, it is more likely for the first agent to receive a more favourable bundle

according to their valuation compared to the second agent.

Minimum Price of Fairness for n-arbitrary agents: This algorithm is exclusively used for the scenario that includes 10 agents. Thus, its results are displayed in Table 4.9. It presents remarkably similar behaviour to the ECE algorithm. Once again, we observe how the increase in goods significantly impacts the outcomes with a notable rise in the percentages of EF and EFX allocations. It is logical for this algorithm to present similar patterns to ECE, as it uses ECE for partial allocation in its final step.

algorithm		Fairness percentages			
		20 goods	100 goods	500 goods	1000 goods
Round-Robin	%EF	6.3	100	100	100
	%EFX	94.8	100	100	100
ECE	%EF	0.8	53.8	99.5	100
	%EFX	43.2	64.5	99.5	100
Min-PoF	%EF	0.4	51.4	99.9	100
	%EFX	41.1	60.4	99.9	100

Table 4.9: Fairness metrics when handling 10 agents.

The graphs corresponding to this experiment can be found in Appendix A.

Conclusions

There is a consistent and common pattern across most algorithms, indicating an improvement of the fairness metrics with the increase in the number of goods. This phenomenon occurs because with a larger number of goods, there is a higher likelihood of agents receiving their preferred goods, consequently decreasing the overall envy of the system. Among the individual algorithms, the one that exhibits superior performance with almost perfect scores across all scenarios is Round-Robin. On the other hand, ECE, despite prioritizing envy minimization, fails to outperform RR but still achieves commendable results. On the contrary, the Min-PoF for 2 agents displays notably lower percentages of EF and EFX allocations, with a decreasing trend when good quantities grow. Finally, the Min-PoF for n-arbitrary agents mirrors ECE's behaviour, achieving satisfactory results.

4.4 Experiments to analyse runtime

The analysis and comparison of the runtime complexities of various algorithms is key for determining the optimal and most efficient approach to solving a given task. In the context of allocating goods among multiple agents, this process is essential to identify the algorithm that minimizes the computational resources while still achieving the desired outcome.

4.4.1 Runtime evaluation of RR, ECE and Min-PoF algorithms with Spliddit data.

For the execution of this experiment, we use set-up 1 (Section 4.2.1), which includes all the Spliddit instances. For each of the algorithms (RR, ECE and its modification, and Min-PoF for n -arbitrary agents), we calculate the average runtime of all the instances and take this as the representative runtime of that algorithm. Considering the simplicity of RR, our initial hypothesis is that it exhibits the lowest runtime.

Results

Round-Robin: The results confirmed our original prediction. The RR algorithm has the shortest runtime, with an average of $3.14e - 05$ seconds, where it computes allocations in polynomial time. For our implementation, the runtime complexity is $O(n * m)$, where n is the number of agents and m is the number of goods.

Envy-cycle elimination: This algorithm achieves a longer runtime compared to RR with an average of $1.20e - 04$ seconds as shown in Table 4.10. Despite this, the runtime remains within acceptable bounds. It is logical that the ECE exhibits a higher runtime since it is a more complex algorithm. In each iteration, it examines whether a cycle exists, which requires going through all the agents and assessing their envy towards the others. Additionally, if a cycle is detected, goods must be reallocated, leading to another round of assessment for all the agents involved in the cycle. Nevertheless, despite exhibiting a longer runtime than RR, the time complexity of ECE remains polynomial, which ensures its computational efficiency.

Modification of Envy-cycle Elimination: This is a variation of ECE: once all goods have been distributed, it checks if there is a cycle and if so, it solves it. Intuitively, this would increase the runtime as we are doing the process of checking and solving cycles one extra time. This implies the iteration through all the agents at least one more time. Our hypothesis was indeed confirmed with the results, as the average runtime for this algorithm is $1.23e - 04$ seconds, a slightly larger value than for the original ECE.

	Round-Robin	ECE	Modified ECE	Min-PoF
Runtime (seconds)	3.14e-05	1.20e-04	1.23e-04	1.23e-04

Table 4.10: Runtime comparison of algorithms with Spliddit data.

Minimum Price of Fairness: Finally, for this algorithm, we obtain an average runtime per instance of $1.23e - 04$ seconds. This is, along with the modified ECE, the highest runtime of all the tested algorithms, which is not surprising because of the implementation of the algorithm itself. This algorithm first computes the maximum social welfare allocation, and from here, it creates some partial allocations. On top of this, it uses the envy-cycle elimination to expand these partial allocations to complete ones. Only the creation of the partial allocations involves multiple iterations through all the agents and goods. Since the algorithm itself uses the ECE algorithm, it is reasonable that the Minimum Price of Fairness has a larger runtime than the other algorithms.

Conclusions

As anticipated, the Round-Robin emerges as the fastest algorithm due to its straightforward implementation and being the one that involves the least iterations over the agents and goods. Consequently, if our objective is uniquely to maximize the process efficiency, employing RR for the allocation of the goods would be adequate. Nonetheless, even though the other three algorithms exhibit a slower runtime, they showcase a satisfactory performance, with all runtime metrics remaining in the range of microseconds. This highlights their suitability for a practical application despite their slightly longer execution times.

4.4.2 Runtime evaluation of RR, ECE and Min-PoF algorithms with generated data.

To conduct this experiment, we utilize set-up 2 (Section 4.2.2) and 3 (Section 4.2.3). For both scenarios we have an increasing number of goods and a constant number of agents, two for set-up 2 and ten for set-up 3. As it was formerly mentioned, we generate 1000 instances for each number of goods and we calculate the average runtime for each of them.

Given both set-ups and bearing in mind the number of agents involved in each, it is appropriate to use different versions of the Minimum Price of Fairness algorithm for each scenario: the one designed for two agents for set-up 2 and the one tailored for n-arbitrary agents for set-up 3. Additionally, we study the runtime of the Round-Robin and the Envy-cycle Elimination algorithm.

Results

Following the experiment's execution, as shown in Figures 4.6 and 4.7, a clear trend emerges: as the number of goods increases, the runtime also grows. This is a rather intuitive notion, as the greater the number of goods to iterate through, the more computationally expensive the process becomes. Even though the three algorithms adhere to this pattern, their runtimes significantly differ from each other. This can clearly be observed in Tables 4.11 and 4.12.

Algorithm	Execution Time (s)				
	10 goods	20 goods	100 goods	500 goods	1000 goods
Round-robin	3.45×10^{-5}	7.05×10^{-5}	5.56×10^{-4}	7.80×10^{-3}	2.81×10^{-2}
ECE	9.41×10^{-5}	1.91×10^{-4}	1.38×10^{-3}	2.26×10^{-2}	8.50×10^{-2}
Min-POF	2.21×10^{-4}	1.51×10^{-3}	1.62×10^{-1}	62.04	162.87

Table 4.11: Performance Efficiency Metrics when handling 2 agents.

Round-Robin: This algorithm maintains the already observed swift runtime in Experiment 4.4.1. In both scenarios, involving 2 and 10 agents, there is a noticeable rise in runtime when handling 1000 goods; however, the execution time remains below one-tenth of a second. The escalation in the number of agents also has a direct impact on the runtime, with a slightly higher runtime when the agent count reaches 10. Nonetheless,

this experiment, alongside Experiment 4.4.1, highlights the computational efficiency of the Round-Robin algorithm.

Envy-cycle Elimination: This algorithm exhibits similar behaviour to RR; where an increase in the number of goods results in a corresponding rise in runtime. The most significant leap occurs when transitioning from 500 to 1000 goods; for instance, with 10 agents, the runtime escalates by approximately 0.4 seconds. Nonetheless, unlike Round-Robin, the ECE is noticeably more affected by the augmentation of the number of agents, displaying considerably higher runtimes when the agent count reaches 10.

This is logical as the ECE entails multiple iterations through the agents, especially during the cycle detection and resolution steps. Consequently, while ECE effectively handles a large number of goods, its efficiency starts to decline as the number of agents increases. However, even with this last consideration, the maximum recorded runtime is around 0.5 seconds, which still falls within an acceptable execution time range.

Algorithm	Execution Time (s)			
	20 goods	100 goods	500 goods	1000 goods
Round-robin	7.97×10^{-5}	5.90×10^{-4}	8.31×10^{-3}	2.76×10^{-2}
ECE	1.13×10^{-3}	8.04×10^{-3}	1.41×10^{-1}	5.32×10^{-1}
Min-PoF	8.06×10^{-4}	8.78×10^{-3}	1.50×10^{-1}	5.66×10^{-1}

Table 4.12: Performance Efficiency Metrics when handling 10 agents.

Figure 4.6: Runtime comparison for different algorithms when handling a constant number of 2 agents and increasing number of goods.

Minimum Price of Fairness for 2 agents: The outcomes of this algorithm are included in Table 4.11, revealing a trend of escalating runtimes with an increasing number of goods, consistent with the previous algorithms. However, the Min-PoF exhibits notably longer execution times. While it maintains runtimes below a second up to 100 goods,

there is a sharp increase starting from 500 goods, reaching an average runtime of nearly three minutes for 1000 goods. This substantial increase in the execution time could be attributed to the algorithm's implementation itself, which currently includes a nested *for* loop that iterates through all the goods. Consequently, it is reasonable for the runtime to rapidly escalate with a larger number of goods.

Minimum Price of Fairness for n-arbitrary agents: The results generated by this algorithm, as illustrated in Table 4.12, reveal a significantly improved performance compared to the version designed for just 2 agents, maintaining execution times below one second across all the number of goods. The most sharp increase in runtime occurs when transitioning from 100 to 500 goods, for which the execution time extends by almost 0.15 seconds. Hence, it can be inferred that this algorithm shows superior performance when dealing with a number of goods not too large. As demonstrated in Experiment 4.4.1, the runtime of the Minimum Price of Fairness for n-arbitrary agents is marginally higher than for the ECE due to the integration of the ECE within its own implementation.

Figure 4.7: Runtime comparison for different algorithms when handling a constant number of 10 agents and increasing number of goods.

Conclusions

Among the analysed algorithms, Round-Robin stands out for its efficient execution, regardless of the number of agents or goods it handles. Even though the Envy-cycle elimination also exhibits short execution times, it shows a slightly higher sensitivity to the increase in the number of agents due to its iterative nature during cycle detection and resolution. Moreover, the Minimum Price of Fairness for 2 agents displays notably longer runtimes, particularly when dealing with 500 and 1000 goods. This can be due to potential inefficiencies within its implementation as it contains a nested loop structure that iterates through all the goods. In contrast, the Minimum Price of Fairness for n-arbitrary agents achieves a notably improved performance, consistently maintaining execution times below one second across all good quantities. This algorithm particularly

exhibits a good performance for a moderate number of goods. Overall, the experiment underscores the importance of selecting algorithms tailored to specific scenarios and performance demands.

4.5 Experiments to analyse price of fairness

Another relevant concept related to the fair distribution of goods is the price of fairness of the computed allocations. Recall that social welfare is defined as the sum of the valuations of the agents for the goods they receive. The price of fairness measures how much social welfare is sacrificed to ensure fairness of the allocation. It is defined as the ratio between the maximum social welfare that can be achieved and the social welfare obtained when the allocation is fair, with the optimal price of fairness being 1. Therefore, the comparison of the price of fairness achieved by various algorithms is key in evaluating their ability to balance fairness and efficiency in resource allocation.

4.5.1 Price of Fairness analysis of RR, ECE and Min-PoF with Splid-dit data

In this experiment, we utilize set-up 1 (Section 4.2.1). Four algorithms are used to determine the allocations: RR, ECE, the modification of the latter, and the Min-PoF for n -arbitrary agents. For this experiment, we calculate the average price of fairness across all instances for each algorithm, considering it as a representative measure for that algorithm. Initially, an intuitive hypothesis might suggest that the Min-PoF algorithm, as its name implies, is the one that shows a superior performance.

Results

Minimum Price of Fairness for n -agents: Our initial hypothesis is confirmed. The Minimum Price of Fairness algorithm exhibits the lowest price of fairness with an average of 1.09, the closest value to the optimal price of fairness among the four analysed algorithms as shown in Table 4.13. This can be attributed to the algorithm's first step, where it computes the maximum social welfare allocation for the given instance. Subsequently, it generates partial allocations where agents select their most valued good from their assigned ones. This approach evidently prioritizes the computation of an allocation with the highest possible social welfare while maintaining fairness. Nevertheless, this algorithm appears to have a trade-off in terms of runtime, as in Experiment 4.4.1, it showed the worst execution time. This suggests that in scenarios where the minimization of the price of fairness is of great importance, the Min-PoF algorithm would still be preferred despite its operational time not being optimal.

Round-Robin: The next best-performing algorithm is RR, with an average price of fairness of 1.14. This is logical since, in the Round-Robin algorithm, for each round, the agents choose the good they value the most, which is beneficial for maximising social welfare.

ECE and modified version: Lastly, we consider the ECE and its modified version. Although the modification showed marginally better results, neither achieved optimal

outcomes in terms of the price of fairness. This can be explained by the implementation of the algorithms themselves, which focus on minimising the envy between the agents. When minimising envy, it is possible for these algorithms to produce allocations with reduced social welfare as they prioritize fairness over the maximization of social welfare.

	Round-Robin	ECE	Modified ECE	Min-PoF
Price of Fairness	1.14	1.20	1.17	1.09

Table 4.13: Price of Fairness comparison for different algorithms with Spliddit data.

Conclusions

The Minimum Price of Fairness algorithm emerges as the top performer, achieving an average price of fairness of 1.09, closely approaching the optimal value for this metric. However, this achievement is accompanied by the second least efficient runtime of the analysed algorithms. On the other hand, the Round-Robin algorithm exhibits the second-best performance in terms of price of fairness while striking a better balance with runtime efficiency. In Experiment 4.4.1, it obtained the fastest execution time. In contrast, both the ECE algorithm and its variant produce inferior results in relation to the price of fairness. In conclusion, if we are prioritizing fairness, Min-PoF would be the best algorithm, while those seeking a balance between efficiency and price of fairness might prefer Round-Robin.

4.5.2 Price of Fairness analysis of RR, ECE and Min-PoF with generated data

As in Experiment 4.4.2, we employ set-up 2 (Section 4.2.2) and set-up 3 (Section 4.2.3). We maintain a consistent number of agents, either 2 or 10, while gradually increasing the number of goods to be distributed. For each specified number of goods, we generate 1000 instances and compute the average price of fairness across all instances. The analysed algorithms are RR, ECE, Min-PoF for 2 agents (uniquely used for set-up 2) and the Min-PoF for n-arbitrary agents (exclusively used for set-up 3).

Results

The outcomes of this experiment, depicted in Figures 4.8 and 4.9, reveal a consistent pattern: an improvement of the price of fairness as the number of goods grows. Through improvement, we understand that the values are converging towards 1, which is considered the optimal price of fairness. This trend can be attributed to the broader availability of resources to distribute as the number of goods increases. Consequently, it becomes easier to find allocations that satisfy the fairness criteria while maximizing overall social welfare. This trend holds true for all the algorithms except the Minimum Price of Fairness for 2 agents.

Round-Robin: This algorithm consistently demonstrates a low price of fairness across various good numbers for both 2 and 10 agents. Its performance remains steady and

tends to improve with the rise of the number of goods, suggesting its effective scalability in handling larger good quantities.

Envy-cycle Elimination: It exhibits a similar behaviour to Round-Robin but with slightly higher price of fairness values. As previously discussed in Experiment 4.5.1, ECE prioritizes the minimization of the envy among agents over the maximization of the social welfare of the final allocation. Once again, the number of goods will lead to an improvement in the metric. Additionally, it is worth noting that the augmentation of the number of agents also impacts the price of fairness, with marginally higher values when there are 10 agents.

Algorithm	Price of Fairness				
	10 goods	20 goods	100 goods	500 goods	1000 goods
Round-robin	1.0347	1.0177	1.0045	1.0009	1.0005
ECE	1.0485	1.0276	1.0089	1.0019	1.0009
Min-PoF	1.0259	1.0158	1.0180	1.0164	1.0160

Table 4.14: Price of Fairness when handling 2 agents.

Minimum Price of Fairness for 2 agents: The results for this algorithm are included in Table 4.14. It initially exhibits the lowest price of fairness for a small number of goods (10-20), but it experiences a decline as the good count grows. This is evident in Figure 4.8, where a transition from 20 to 100 goods results in an escalation in the value of the price of fairness, which breaks the pattern observed in all other algorithms. The deviation occurs because the algorithm is designed to achieve the minimum price of fairness under worst-case scenarios. However, it is possible that the generated instances do not reflect such scenarios, resulting in other algorithms outperforming it.

Algorithm	Price of Fairness			
	20 goods	100 goods	500 goods	1000 goods
Round-robin	1.0788	1.0196	1.0046	1.0024
ECE	1.0874	1.0272	1.0078	1.0043
Min POF	1.0936	1.0394	1.0106	1.0056

Table 4.15: Price of Fairness when handling 10 agents.

Minimum Price of Fairness for n-arbitrary agent: Lastly, this algorithm follows the general trend of improving price of fairness when the number of goods increases. Despite its name implying otherwise, it presents the worst values in terms of price of fairness. Similar to its counterpart for 2 agents, this algorithm targets the minimum price of fairness for the worst-case scenarios, which might align with the characteristics of our generated data.

Conclusions

Despite our initial thoughts of the Min-PoF algorithms yielding superior results, both are designed to obtain the minimum price of fairness for the worst-case scenario.

Nevertheless, for our instances that might not adhere to such case, other simpler algorithms like Round-Robin show better performance. Additionally, the increasing number of goods results in a lower price of fairness values, as there are more resources available to distribute and agents are more likely to obtain their preferred goods.

Figure 4.8: Price of Fairness of different algorithms when handling a constant number of 2 agents and increasing number of goods.

Figure 4.9: Price of Fairness of different algorithms when handling a constant number of 10 agents and increasing number of goods.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

Fair allocation of indivisible goods is primarily a theoretical domain with scarce empirical investigation. Given the interdisciplinary significance of the topic, it becomes essential to provide some experimental data. Consequently, we conducted multiple experiments aimed at studying the performance of existing algorithms to solve fair allocations. Our focus lay on analysing fairness metrics, evaluating runtime and assessing the price of fairness. Additionally, the implemented algorithms will be available for the scientific community to use in further experiments.

The executed experiments have led to significant findings. Throughout the project, Round-Robin consistently exhibited superior performance, particularly excelling in runtime efficiency given its straightforward and simple implementation. Additionally, it demonstrated favourable outcomes in terms of the price of fairness metric.

The Envy-cycle Elimination algorithm, slightly more complex than RR, consistently achieved superior results, especially in fairness metrics. Notably, it generated a remarkable number of α -EFX allocations where α exceeded the theoretical EFX benchmark guarantee. Thus, given ECE's optimal performance, its utilization instead of the more complex algorithm designed to consistently surpass the theoretical benchmark appears appropriate.

On the contrary, more complex algorithms, such as the two versions of Minimum Price of Fairness, which we initially anticipated to excel in the price of fairness metric, actually achieved poorer results than the other two algorithms. The Min-PoF algorithms are designed to obtain optimal outcomes in the worst-case scenarios, which was not the case of the instances used in our study.

The main takeaway is that simpler algorithms, such as Round-Robin and Envy-cycle Elimination, outperformed the more complex and resource-consuming algorithms. Hence, when not confronted with worst-case scenarios, opting for these two algorithms would be suitable.

5.1 MInf part 2: Future work

All the executed experiments and conclusions drawn are under the assumption that the agents involved in the allocation are non-strategic. However, what occurs when agents are strategic? In such instances, an agent might intentionally misrepresent their valuation of an item in order to obtain a better bundle. This introduces a new layer of difficulty to the already challenging task of fair allocation, as the distribution is supposed to align with the agents' *true* valuations.

There is already existing work related to this topic, including the creation of *truthful mechanisms* where agents have no incentive to lie (Caragiannis et al., 2009). However, significant questions still remain open, such as the existence of Pure Nash equilibrium allocations with stronger guarantees than EF1. Exploring these questions, along with an in-depth study of game theory and how strategic agents might impact the algorithms analysed in this dissertation, will be the primary focus of next year's research. Additionally, we could further investigate algorithms for fair allocation and related concepts such as proportionality (Steinhaus, 1949), Maximin Share (MMS) (Amanatidis et al., 2022) or chore division (Dehghani et al., 2018).

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Appendix A

Additional graphs for Experiment 4.3.5

Figure A.1: Percentages of EF allocations for different algorithms when handling a constant number of 2 agents and increasing number of items.

Figure A.2: Percentages of EFX allocations for different algorithms when handling a constant number of 2 agents and increasing number of items.

Figure A.3: Percentages of EF allocations for different algorithms when handling a constant number of 10 agents and increasing number of items.

Figure A.4: Percentages of EFX allocations for different algorithms when handling a constant number of 10 agents and increasing number of items.